

Supplementary Materials

Supplementary Table S1. Search strategies used in each database.

Database	Search strategy	Results
MEDLINE/PubMed	(((frail elderly[MeSH Terms]) OR frail*[Title])) AND (Brazil*) AND (((((((((((aged[MeSH Terms]) OR older adult*[Title/Abstract]) OR oldest old[Title/Abstract]) OR elder*[Title/Abstract]) OR old age[Title/Abstract]) OR ageing[Title/Abstract]) OR geriatr*[Title/Abstract]) OR later life[Title/Abstract]) OR oldest-old[Title/Abstract]))))	582
LILACS	(frail elderly OR idoso fragilizado OR frail OR fragilidade) AND (brasil* OR brazil*) AND (idoso* OR envelhecimento OR aged OR elder* OR ageing OR geriatr*)	325
SciELO	(frail elderly OR idoso fragilizado OR frail OR fragilidade) AND (brasil* OR brazil*) AND (idoso* OR envelhecimento OR aged OR elder* OR ageing OR geriatr*)	308
Scopus	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (frail*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (brazil*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (older OR elder* OR aged OR aging OR "late* life" OR geriatr*	510

	OR oldest-old)) AND (EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR , 2000) OR EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR , 1998))	
CINAHL	((MH "Brazil") OR TX brazil* OR brasil*) AND (TX frail* OR (MH "Frail Elderly") OR (MH "Frailty Syndrome") OR TX fragilidade) AND (TX (older OR elder* OR geriatr* OR aged OR aging OR "later life" OR "oldest-old" OR idoso*) OR (MH "Aged"))	795
EMBASE	'frail elderly'/exp OR 'frailty'/exp OR frail*:ab,ti) AND brazil*:ab,ti AND [2001-2024]/py	472
PEDro	brazil* (title) AND frailty (problem)	13
AgeLine	TX frail* AND TX brazil*	38
JBI	frail*; brazil*	3
	TOTAL	3046

Supplementary Table S2. Eligible studies excluded from the quantitative synthesis due to insufficient data

First author	Publication year	Full title	Journal/ source
Diniz et al.	2022	Cognitive frailty is associated with elevated pro-inflammatory markers and a higher risk of mortality	American Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry
Santiago et al.	2018	Predictive validity of the Brazilian version of the Tilburg Frailty Indicator for adverse health outcomes in older adults	Archives of Gerontology and Geriatrics
Bregola et al.	2022	Accumulated cognitive impairment, frailty, burden, and perceived stress and the risk of hospitalization and mortality in older caregivers	Dementia & Neuropsychologia

Santos et al.	2022	Maximum expiratory pressure is a good predictor of the incidence of the frailty syndrome in elderly men]	Ciência & Saúde Coletiva
Garcia et al.	2016	Identification of Clinical and Functional Falls Risk Factors Among Low Bone Density Older Women: A Longitudinal Study	Topics in Geriatric Rehabilitation
Fhon et al.	2021	Frailty and sociodemographic and health factors, and social support network in the Brazilian elderly: A longitudinal study	Revista da Escola de Enfermagem da USP
Tavares et al.	2021	Health status of older men and women: longitudinal study	Revista Enfermagem UERJ

Note: Quantitative synthesis refers to the meta-analysis. The studies listed in this table met the eligibility criteria for the systematic review but were excluded from the quantitative synthesis because the data required to estimate frailty and/or prefrailty incidence or frailty status transitions were not available in the published articles and were not obtained after author contact.

Supplementary Table S3. Incident cases and person-years used in the meta-analysis of frailty incidence among older adults.

Study	Incident cases	Person-years	Incidence rate per 1000 PY
Da Silva et al. ¹⁶	16	187	86
Lenardt et al. ³⁰	3	200	15
Rocha et al. ²⁹	1	90	11
De Jesus et al. ³⁵	82	505	162
Carneiro et al. ³⁴	39	914	43
Alves et al. ²⁶	87	3052	29
Neri et al. ²⁸	113	4446	25
Alencar et al. ²⁵	30	147	204
Gomes, et al. ²⁷	57	534	107
Saraiva et al. ³³	239	821	291
Aprahamian et al. ³¹	45	340	132
Borges et al. ³²	22	113	195
Fhon et al. ¹⁵	91	1080	84

Supplementary Table S4. Incident cases and person-years used in the meta-analysis of prefrailty incidence among older adults.

Study	Incident cases	Person-years	Incidence rate per 1000 PY
Da Silva et al. ¹⁶	23	67	343
Lenardt et al. ³⁰	53	200	265
Rocha et al. ²⁹	15	30	500
De Jesus et al. ³⁵	40	279	143
Carneiro et al. ³⁴	32	609	53
Alves et al. ²⁶	207	1648	126
Neri et al. ²⁸	91	1656	55
Alencar et al. ²⁵	14	43	326
Gomes, et al. ²⁷	61	158	386
Saraiva et al. ³³	59	168	351
Aprahamian et al. ³¹	45	76	592
Fhon et al. ¹⁵	36	780	46

Note: PY = person-years. Borges et al., 2021 was not included in the prefrailty incidence meta-analysis due to unavailable data on incident prefrailty.

Supplementary Table S5. Methodological quality assessment of studies included in the meta-analysis using the JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist.

Included studies	JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist										Score	%
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9			
Neri et al. ²⁸	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Y	7	77.8	
Aprahamian et al. ³¹	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	6	66.7	
Lenardt et al. ³⁰	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	7	77.8	
Fhon et al. ¹⁵	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N	7	77.8	
Alves et al. ²⁶	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N	7	77.8	
Alencar et al., 2013 ²⁵	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N	6	66.7	
De Jesus et al., 2021 ³⁵	Y	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	N	6	66.7	
Carneiro et al., 2019 ³⁴	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	8	88.9	
Borges et al., 2021 ³²	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N	7	77.8	
Saraiva et al., 2020 ³³	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N	6	66.7	
Gomes et al., 2018 ²⁷	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N	5	55.6	
Rocha et al., 2023 ²⁹	Y	N	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N	4	44.4	
Da Silva et al., 2015 ¹⁶	Y	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	6	66.7	

Note. Y, yes; N, no; JBI, Joanna Briggs Institute. Items 1–9 correspond to the domains of the JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist for prevalence and incidence studies.

Supplementary Fig S1. Forest plot of subgroup analysis according to frailty assessment instrument in the meta-analysis of frailty incidence among older adults.

Supplementary Fig S2. Forest plot of subgroup analysis according to recruitment setting in the meta-analysis of frailty incidence among older adults.

Supplementary Fig S3. Forest plot of subgroup analysis according to frailty assessment instrument in the meta-analysis of prefrailty incidence among older adults.

Supplementary Fig S4. Forest plot of subgroup analysis according to recruitment setting in the meta-analysis of prefrailty incidence among older adults.

Supplementary Table S6. Estimates of Leave-One-Out Sensitivity Analyses for the Incidence of frailty.

Study	Point estimate	Lower CI	Upper CI
Da Silva et al, 2015 ¹⁶	96	72	121
Lenardt et al., 2024 ³⁰	104	78	129
Rocha et al., 2023 ²⁹	104	78	129
De Jesus et al., 2021 ³⁵	89	66	113
Carneiro et al., 2019 ³⁴	102	75	128
Alves et al., 2021 ²⁶	106	73	140
Neri et al, 2022 ²⁸	107	73	140
Alencar et al., 2013 ²⁵	90	66	114
Gomes, et al., 2018 ²⁷	94	70	119
Saraiva et al., 2020 ³³	74	56	93
Aprahamian et al., 2019 ³¹	92	68	116
Borges et al., 2021 ³²	91	67	115
Fhon et al., 2018 ¹⁵	97	72	121

Note: Point estimates and confidence intervals are presented as cases per 1000 person-years (PY). CI = confidence interval.

Supplementary Table S7. Estimates of Leave-One-Out Sensitivity Analyses for the Incidence of prefrailty.

Study	Point estimate	Lower CI	Upper CI
Da Silva et al, 2015 ¹⁶	191	147	236
Lenardt et al., 2024 ³⁰	191	147	236
Rocha et al., 2023 ²⁹	193	149	237
De Jesus et al., 2021 ³⁵	209	162	256
Carneiro et al., 2019 ³⁴	229	178	281
Alves et al., 2021 ²⁶	216	166	265
Neri et al, 2022 ²⁸	236	179	292
Alencar et al., 2013 ²⁵	195	150.	239
Gomes., et al., 2018 ²⁷	180	137	223
Saraiva et al., 2020 ³³	183	139	226
Aprahamian et al., 2019 ³¹	180	137	222
Fhon et al., 2018 ¹⁵	232	179	285

Note: Point estimates and confidence intervals are presented as cases per 1000 person-years (PY). CI = confidence interval.